

UNIVERSITÀ DEGLI STUDI DI PERUGIA

DIPARTIMENTO DI FISICA E GEOLOGIA

*Corso di Laurea Magistrale in
Geology for Energy Resources*

UNIVERSITÀ DEGLI STUDI
DI PERUGIA

TESI DI LAUREA

EFFECT OF THE CO₂ ON THE LOG RESPONSE: HOW CAN WE DEAL
WITH IT FOR A SOUND FORMATION EVALUATION, PRACTICAL
APPROACH

Laureando:

Elvin Babayev

Relatore:

Massimiliano Porreca

Correlatore:

Maurizio Mele, Marco Pirrone,
Piero Balossino

Anno Accademico 2021/2022

Abstract

This study presents the summary of the end-of-studies internship carried out in the ENI (Ente Nazionale Idrocarburi) Company, for completing the thesis of the master's program in "Geology for Energy Resources".

The aim of this research is to examine the origin, generation, migration, sink of carbon dioxide, and its properties and measurement methods, and to simulate several scenarios so as to assess the impact of CO₂ on log responses.

Firstly, the main origins of carbon dioxide, the possible escape pathway in the reservoir/wellbore, then its physical and non-physical properties from reference data have been discussed. Furthermore, the most advanced simulator developed by the University of Austin has been employed to analyze the log response of the CO₂ which is rarely examined in order to distinguish it from other reservoir gases. Subsequently, to check the accuracy of the simulator's performance, the simulated physical properties of the carbon gas have been compared with the reference data from the National Institute of Standards and Technology. Here, simulated results are presented in tables and graphs.

Finally, this study has shown that it is not easy to distinguish CO₂ from CH₄, and other hydrocarbon gases using analytical techniques but mentioned the importance of the analysis of CO₂ in reservoir condition. According to quantitative simulation outcomes, neutron porosity has been identified as the appropriate instrument for monitoring carbon dioxide movement in the certain study.

Acknowledgment

Without the assistance of several people, this work would not have been accomplished. I am grateful to my professor, Massimiliano Porreca for taking his valuable time and assisting me throughout this period.

Many thanks to my supervisors, Maurizio Mele, Piero Balossino, and Marco Pirrone who reviewed my several edits and helped me in making some of the confusing issues clear.

This work has been assisted and funded thanks to the collaboration between the University of Perugia and Eni S.p.A. I would like to express my gratitude to the ENI and the University of Perugia for awarding me a Dissertation Internship, and for providing me with the financial means to complete this project.

Table of Contents

Abstract	2
Introduction	6
Chapter 1. Origin of Carbon dioxide	8
1.1 Organic sources.....	8
1.2 Inorganic sources	10
Chapter 2. Using the stable isotope concept to define the source of naturally occurring carbon dioxide in the geosphere	13
Chapter 3. Possible sink of CO₂	15
Chapter 4. Migration of CO₂	16
4.1 Potential migration channels: faults and fractures	17
4.2 Seal capacity of caprock and breakthrough pressure	17
4.3 Anthropogenic pathways	19
Chapter 5. Physical properties of CO₂	20
5.1 Density	21
5.2 Hydrogen Index	22
5.3 Acoustic velocity	23
Chapter 6. Well-logging	25
6.1 Natural Gamma Logging	25
6.2 Neutron Porosity Logging.....	27
6.3 Resistivity Logging	32
Chapter 7. Analysis of the pure fluid response of CO₂ for density, neutron, and sigma	35
7.1 Validation of UtapWels response against benchmark situation.....	35
7.2 Density simulation	38
7.3 Neutron simulation.....	38
7.4 Sigma simulation	40

7.5 Acoustic velocity	41
Chapter 8. Building synthetic well-logs for several scenarios in CO₂	
Injection and storage project	43
8.1 Case N.1 Pre-injection period and the base model	45
8.2 Case N.2. CO ₂ injection (1 year) and tool response.....	47
Case N.3. CO ₂ injection (2 years) and tool response.	49
Chapter 9. Validating formation evaluation of a reservoir containing	
CO₂	53
Conclusion.....	55
Reference.....	56

Introduction

Carbon dioxide is a critical part of the Earth's carbon cycle, which is a group of mechanisms that cycle carbon in various forms throughout our planet. Both natural and man-made systems constantly emit carbon dioxide. The importance of carbon gas for our world and living beings is undeniable. Along with the benefits it gives to the natural eco system, it also has disadvantages such as an increase in global temperature, increase in costs in the energy sector, and can lead to serious health problems. For these reasons, studying, monitoring, and observing CO₂ sources is one of the most important issues of today. As the focus of this study is on the energy industry, we will only discuss its impact on the energy industry.

The source and spread of CO₂ are crucial for the assessment of risk before drilling because it lowers the economic value of natural gas through the diluting of hydrocarbon concentrations and increases the cost of the industrial processes for treating and separating the gas because of its corrosive nature.

The main purpose of the experimental part of this work is to utilize UtapWels to simulate log response in the reservoir saturated with CO₂ in combination with other native fluids (water and hydrocarbons). UtapWels (University of Texas at Austin Petrophysical and Well Log Simulator) is a software platform set up by the University of Austin within the activity of FEJIRC (Formation Evaluation Joint Industrial Research Consortium). Eni has been part of this international consortium for more than 15 years. The FEJIRC is led by the University of Texas at Austin and it is participated by Operating and Service Company. The main target of this software is to construct an accurate earth model, petrophysically consistent, and in agreement with all measurements, with the goal to perform Formation Evaluation based on Log Modelling. Log modeling capability allows for the simulation of all types of logging measurements given an assessed earth model. Earth Model is composed of the following elements:

- 1) Geometry

- Layers around the borehole
 - Radial Zones for mud filtrate invasion evaluation
- 2) Properties of matrix rocks and fluids
- Physical properties (directly correlated to logs. Gr, Resistivity...)
 - Petrophysical properties

The experimental job has been performed based on the following goals:

- 1) Validation of UtapWels response against benchmark situation for pure fluid
- 2) Analysis of the pure fluid response of CO₂
- 3) Simulating Log response for evaluation of CO₂ plume distribution in Storage project.
- 4) Validating formation evaluation of a reservoir containing CO₂

Chapter 1. Origin of Carbon dioxide

1.1 Organic sources

a) Biogenic processes

Biogenic carbon dioxide is carbon dioxide released due to the decay of organic material, biomass, and its subsidiaries. In the anaerobic state, when oxygen is not present, bacterial activity takes over and accelerates the decomposition of the biomass. Emitted CO₂ from decayed material is not considered a greenhouse gas emission and becomes part of the biogenic carbon cycle if it comes from a sustainable source, while non-biogenic CO₂ from fossil fuels remains locked in the ground for millions of years.

b) CO₂ from thermal maturation of organic matter

One of the main organic sources of Carbon dioxide is the thermal breakdown of kerogen during early catagenesis. Kerogens are organic compounds formed from plants and animal organic matter that are deposited in sediments. High levels of kerogen characterize petroleum source rocks. Source rocks are mostly mudstones and shales with finely dispersed kerogen. A maturation process occurs when kerogen-rich rocks are buried deeper under other strata in actively subsiding sedimentary basins, causing them to transform into other compounds by heat and pressure, which is called maturation. Kerogen can be classified into different categories depending on the source of the kerogen:

- Type I algal kerogen - obtained mostly from algae
- Type II liptinitic kerogen - derived primarily from plankton
- Type III humic kerogen - derived primarily from terrestrial plants

They emit volatiles such as water, methane, and carbon dioxide during this process. Kerogen begins to decompose at temperatures ranging from 75⁰C to 120⁰C, with carbon dioxide as the major byproduct. The amount of carbon dioxide produced by the maturation of huge quantities of gas-prone source rock can be significant. The carbon content of the kerogen grows as it matures because there is a proportionately larger loss of hydrogen and oxygen than carbon. The majority of the hydrogen is lost due to demethylation, that's why the amount of carbon dioxide released by Type III Kerogen is significantly higher than that of Type I Kerogen.

c) Hydrocarbon oxidation by thermochemical sulfate reduction

At greater depth and temperature, hydrocarbons may react with minerals containing sulfate and as a result, CO₂ could be released. However, the amount of CO₂ released is expected to be insignificant. Additionally, oil and gas can produce CO₂ through biodegradation. Biodegradation of oil leaking from a salt diapir, for instance, converts it into carbon dioxide as it migrates upwards. In this situation, $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{CO}_2}$ values range from 43.9 to -34‰ (see the stable isotope values in next chapter fig.2).

d) Coal maturation and metamorphism

Coal is mostly made up of organic compounds. It's made from peat by a process called coalification or maturation. As the peat is buried, it exposes a process similar to Type III kerogen maturation, As temperature and pressure rise, lignite transforms into bituminous coal, then anthracite. The major volatiles during coal formation, from lignite to early high-volatile bituminous coal stages, are CO₂ and H₂O. (Boudou et al., 1984). The huge amounts of CO₂ being produced by the vertically adjacent coals could be explained by a relatively high heat flow.

$\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values of organically derived CO₂ typically range between -10 to -30‰. CO₂ produced by thermal maturation of kerogen has a $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ range of -10 to -

25‰ depending on the degree of maturity and the isotopic ratios of the carboxyl group of the original kerogen. Depending on the procedure, bacterial CO₂ has a broad range of δ^{13} +15 to -30‰ (Clayton, 1995; Mattavelli, Ricchiuto, Grignani & Schoell, 1983; Schoell, 1983; Thrasher & Fleet, 1995; Whiticar, 1994) (as shown in fig.2).

1.2 Inorganic sources

a) Mantle degassing

Magma degassing is one of the most significant CO₂ producers. As magma rises to the earth's surface, it loses pressure and degasses. Volcanic activity or intrusion of molten rock into the crust is frequently linked to magma degassing. The amount of gas at a given volcanic location varies greatly depending on the tectonic setting and magma type. In convergent plate boundaries where two plates collide, volcanism is caused by the hydration of the mantle by volatiles released by the subducted tectonic plate. The subducted slab could contain big quantities of carbon in the form of limestones or other sedimentary rocks. Most of the total CO₂ flow from the geosphere is believed to occur through the recycling of crustal carbon into the mantle along convergent plate borders and subsequently back to

Fig1. Model is depicting the link between plate tectonics, volcanism, and the creation of carbon dioxide by contact metamorphism of carbonate rocks.

the surface via volcanoes. But in divergent plate boundaries, ductile mantle material goes up passively into the free space created when the tectonic plates separate. The mantle material partially melts as it rises due to decompression, and the volatile phases dissolve in the molten rock and are emitted to the atmosphere when it erupts. As a result, the CO₂ emitted at mid-ocean ridges is virtually entirely made up of mantle material. The predominant gas released by volcanoes is H₂O (in the form of water vapor). It typically accounts for more than 60% of the overall gas content. CO₂ is the second most prevalent gas, accounting for about 10-40% of total gas content. CO₂ emissions from volcanic activity are estimated to reach around 300 Mt per year while the number accounted for anthropogenic CO₂ emission is only 24Mt. Only Mt Etna is often regarded as being the most actively degassing volcano (British Geological Survey, report number 2005/8). It emits around 25 Mt of CO₂ each year. CO₂ assumed to be produced from the mantle may also be found in places where there appears to be no volcanic activity. This is expected to enter sedimentary basins via deep-seated faults that break in through the crust's base. Whereas recorded examples are uncommon, such accumulations could be more common.

b) Regional and contact metamorphism of carbonate rocks

Magma that forms as a result of the partial melting of the crust usually doesn't reach the surface in its entirety. This is because some of it is trapped below the surface. Occasionally, some of it penetrates deep into the continental crust, where it meets sedimentary rocks and crystallizes to form the giant igneous rocks found in the deep crust. During the process of intrusion, sedimentary rocks beneath the intrusion metamorphose, a phenomenon that is called contact metamorphism, since it is the result of direct contact between the igneous body and the surrounding sedimentary rocks. As a consequence of contact metamorphism, carbonate rocks, such as limestone, can metamorphose into oxides and hydroxides, releasing significant amounts of carbon dioxide. Carbonates, whether

in the basement or in the sedimentary fill, are the possible source to emit significant amounts of CO₂ when temperatures are above 150°C. Meanwhile, regional metamorphism affects large portions of the crust, which includes areas where plates have formerly been colliding, and where mountain belts have evolved. It is a phenomenon found in nature that occurs when the minerals of rocks are buried in the earth deep enough that their mineral structures are affected by the pressures and temperatures of the Earth. It has been proposed that regional metamorphism of limestones, like contact metamorphism, might result in CO₂ production.

$\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values of CO₂ of mantle-derived material usually range from -3 to -8‰ whilst $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ for CO₂ released as a result of carbonate contact metamorphism changes between -2 and -12‰ (Baker et al., 1995; Schoell, 1983; Thrasher & Fleet, 1995). According to the isotopic composition of carbon, we can define existing CO₂ in the reservoir derived from organic or inorganic sources.

Chapter 2. Using the stable isotope concept to define the source of naturally occurring carbon dioxide in the geosphere

One carbon atom and two oxygen atoms make up a CO₂ molecule, which can have varying molecular weights depending on whether one of the two stable carbon isotopes or one of the three stable oxygen isotopes is present. The most common ones are indicated below:

CO₂ - C¹²O¹⁶O¹⁶- molecular weight of about 44

CO₂ - C¹³O¹⁶O¹⁶-molecular weight of about 45

CO₂ - C¹²O¹⁸O¹⁶-molecular weight of about 46

Other carbon and oxygen isotope combinations are possible, although exceedingly rare in nature. The unit of measurement is $\delta^{13}C_{CO_2}$, and values are stated in (‰) “per mil” where negative numbers indicate values less than the standard, while positive ones represent higher values than the standard. The range

Fig. 2 the range of $\delta^{13}C_{CO_2}$ levels predicted in CO₂ obtained from various geological processes. (British Geological Survey, report number 2005/8)

of $\delta^{13}C_{CO_2}$ values obtained in a CO₂ sample is used to define the origin. Fig.2 describes CO₂ origin based on the stable isotope concept.

Stable isotope values for CO₂ from various geological sources:

Mantle derived: -3‰ ~ -8‰

Regional metamorphism: -10‰ ~ 0‰

Contact metamorphism: -12‰ ~ -2‰

Marine carbonates: -2‰ ~ +2‰

Biogenic decay: -30‰ ~ +15‰

Metamorphism of coals: -20‰ ~ -10‰

Breakdown of kerogen: -25‰ ~ -10‰

It is important to note that Carbon Isotope Data do not always offer definitive interpretations due to the possibility of chemical alteration, and are therefore susceptible to being influenced by the mixing of fluid types. It has been shown that noble gases are particularly useful to trace the movement of groundwater fluids because they are chemically inert, which means that their abundances and isotopic compositions do not alter with the passage of time as a result of chemical interactions. When compared to crustal-derived radiogenic He, mantle He is many times greater and more concentrated in ³He. Some study show that the origins of carbon dioxide can be constrained by combining stable carbon isotope data with helium isotope data in the ratio CO₂/³He_{mantle}. In addition to stable carbon isotopes, the unstable radioactive isotope of carbon, ¹⁴C, can aid in determining the source of carbon gas. The existence of considerable levels of ¹⁴C in CO₂ would imply that it is of recent origin.

Chapter 3. Possible sink of CO₂

We said that the carbon content of the kerogen rises as it matures because of a considerably larger loss of hydrogen and oxygen than carbon. Much of the hydrogen is lost due to methane leakage during demethylation and the oxygen is lost by dehydroxylation. Whereas this does not imply that CO₂ is substantial as a component of natural gas. This is due to the fact that carbon dioxide is more soluble than methane, and most of it is likely to dissolve in the water ejected from the rocks during maturation. As a result, deeper buried over pressured reservoirs in the same formation can have more carbon-dioxide content than shallower hydrostatically pressurized reservoirs. Because of its high solubility, CO₂ sinks must be taken into account when estimating CO₂ risk. Every effort should be taken to avoid producing any water since enormous quantities of CO₂ might be solved when the pressure drops as it approaches the surface.

The presence of microorganisms in the well may lead to a loss of certain amounts of CO₂ since microorganisms consume carbon dioxide for their survival.

Chapter 4. Migration of CO₂

Although volcanoes could serve as pathways for mantle CO₂, the magnitude of their influence is uncertain and may be more influenced by their fault distribution rather than size, location, or type. Fluid moves across geological layers inside hydraulically linked pore space, propelled by pressure and density variations. The gas migrates into adjacent formations through two mechanisms. There are two types of flow in the free gas phase: volume flow or slow Darcy flow, and molecular diffusion. Through tightly porous media, CO₂ migrates through caprocks through two-phase flows (gas/water) coupled with capillary effects. As a basic constraint, the sealing pressure of the caprock should be taken into account when studying possible leakage of CO₂. The purpose of this is to prevent the CO₂ from breaking through it. Molecular diffusion is a negligible source of CO₂ leakage through caprock. The long-term containment of CO₂ should focus on the changes in caprock properties caused by the mineralogical reactions. Fluids flow horizontally and vertically inside permeable rocks, although they can be trapped within the subsurface by impermeable layers and structures. The occurrence of natural oil, gas, and CO₂ fields demonstrates that strata may hold fluids and gases for long periods of geological time. The occurrence of natural leaks of oil, gas, and CO₂ indicates that, in certain circumstances, the overburden containment system fails to hold buoyant fluids. CO₂ can be migrated through the overburden layers by geological channels and anthropogenic processes that contribute to leaks. Geological channels comprise faults, fractures, and fluid flow structures, as well as related structures, whereas man-made migration pathways imply wellbores constructed for hydrocarbon exploration, CO₂ storage, or water production.

4.1 Potential migration channels: faults and fractures

It is clear that major crustal faults are involved in the transportation of CO₂, which must be derived either from the mantle or from the regional metamorphism of the basement. Faults are believed to be fluid movement routes, often at low rates across geological timescales. They can either impede or facilitate the movement of fluids in the subsurface. The existence or absence of important fault features is likely to be recognized from seismic reflection data and allow to avoid places where faults may promote undesirable CO₂ migration. However, smaller faults which are not visible on seismic profile data can be common in particular structures, and their impact on CO₂ migration must be considered. The natural seep investigations do offer some insight into how CO₂ could move across overburden faults. Some of the leaking on the subsurface has been linked to faults and low-level seismicity, suggesting that seismic activity is aiding along-fault migration. A fault's capacity to behave as a lateral trap for buoyant fluids like dense-phase CO₂ is determined by the juxtaposition of lithologies in fault-wall blocks, the nature of fault zone rocks, and any differential pressure across the fault.

4.2 Seal capacity of caprock and breakthrough pressure

Either regional or local sealing boundaries are crucial as a means of CO₂ and hydrocarbon transport. An excellent example of a regional seal restricting CO₂ migration is the thick, overpressured Baong Formation in N.Sumatra Basin in Indonesia. Another potential aspect that should be assessed to restrict naturally occurring CO₂ from escaping through the caprock is the sealing ability of the caprock. Caprock's ability to prevent is measured by the magnitude of its breakthrough pressure, also called the sealing pressure. There are a number of connected pores with irregularly large sizes that are just slightly surpassed by the differential pressure across the caprock, permitting the non-wetting phase to flow

through them. The breakthrough pressure is essentially defined by the capillary pressure within the largest pore throats. Therefore, capillary pressure correlation can be used to examine breakthrough pressures. It is possible to identify the capillary pressure P_c in a pore throat as follows:

$$P_c = \frac{2\sigma}{r_p} \cos \theta \quad (1)$$

Where: σ reflects the interfacial tension (*IFT*) between the wetting and non-wetting phases, r_p indicates the radius of the pore throat, while θ indicates the boundary contact angle or the angle formed by their tangents. The formula (1) demonstrates how the IFT, contact angle, and radius of the pore throat affect the capillary pressure and breakthrough pressure of the linked channels for a particular caprock. In particular, the ability of oil and gas to be stored over a geological time is primarily due to the high sealing pressure of the caprock associated with high IFT and the incredibly small size of the caprock pore throats. So when CO_2 is present in an oil reservoir, supercritical CO_2 replaces the original hydrocarbon at the top of the reservoir formation through interaction with the caprock. The breakthrough pressure changes as the IFT varies at the non-wetting/wetting phase contact. According to Table 1, the IFT for the CO_2 /water system is substantially lower than the IFT for oil/water systems.

Systems	Conditions	IFT (mN/m)
Methane/water	10–30 MPa, 40–80°C	48.6–61.7
Carbon Dioxide/water	10–30 MPa, 40–80°C	16–30
Medium oil/water	>6.9 MPa, 54.4–81.1°C	30–35

Table 1. Interfacial tension for different fluids systems

As indicated in Table.1, IFT values for CO₂/water interface are lower than that of CH₄/water, so accordingly, when CO₂ is introduced to replace the existing hydrocarbons at the top of the reservoir, the breakthrough pressure of the same caprock is lower. Caprock’s sealing ability simply suggests that it can't hold methane or carbon gas in the same way, so while capillary pressure blocks methane from further migration through the interconnected pores, it does not prevent carbon dioxide from escaping through the caprock.

Table.2 states the breakthrough pressure of CH₄/water and CO₂/water for different caprock lithologies. Using the data, the CO₂ breakthrough pressure for a caprock is about 21 MPa, indicating that it has a high sealing quality.

Caprock lithology	Non-wetting/wetting system	Breakthrough pressure (MPa)
Claystone, siltstone limestone	Methane/water	0.2–19.8
Pelitic rocks (shales, clays, claystones, siltstones, and mudrock	Methane /water	0.06–6.7
Evaporite	Methane /water	9.2–21.4

Table 2. Caprock breakthrough pressure results

4.3 Anthropogenic pathways

All wellbores have been built to ensure hydraulic isolation between permeable geological units preserving interests in hydrocarbon fields or aquifers for potable water supply. Wells penetrating the storage cap rock might give a direct passage from the reservoir to the surface. Despite careful planning, wellbore integrity can be affected by later physical and chemical changes in and around the wellbore, as

well as construction defects. CO₂ might take advantage of possible paths between the cement and the geological formation or cement, and the well casing to travel.

Chapter 5. Physical properties of CO₂

Carbon dioxide is an important chemical for both the environment and industry. The study of the chemical and physical characteristics of CO₂ at various temperature/pressure settings is vital in all of these industrial and environmental activities, particularly in extreme (high pressure and temperature) situations. CO₂ may exist in three distinct phases depending on pressure and temperature (Fig. 3). In the phase diagram each area represents the range of temperature and pressure combinations across which that phase is stable. The combination of high P and low T (upper left of Fig. 3) corresponds to the solid phase, whereas high temperature and low pressure favor the gas phase (lower right). A supercritical fluid is formed by the combination of high temperature and high pressure (upper right). (Fig. 3).

Within a reservoir, CO₂ is frequently found in supercritical conditions. It has a critical temperature of 31° Celsius and critical pressure of 7.39 MPa. CO₂ will either be a gas or a liquid below these temperatures and pressures. CO₂ could be stored as a pressurized gas or liquid, or in a supercritical (dense) phase, depending on the in-situ temperature and pressure. When compared to conventional natural gas, supercritical CO₂ possesses the dual features of gas and liquid and has distinct physical properties.

The study of the physical properties of supercritical CO₂ is essential for accurate estimations of CO₂-bearing reservoirs based on log data. The physical characteristics of carbon dioxide were determined by simulations and computations. To investigate and quantify the presence of CO₂ in reservoir, the logging acquisition is one the most important data provider, and the acquired data are used for the Formation evaluation process to assess CO₂ presence and quantification. Logs (both wireline and while drilling) are data acquired in the borehole through dedicated equipment that is representative of the Physical

properties of the reservoirs, comprehensive of matrix (minerals) and Fluids (Water, Hydrocarbons, and other fluids including CO₂ if any). One of the most important logging acquisitions for reservoir fluid assessment is a combination of neutron and density logs.

The most fundamental logging assessment approach is a combination of neutron and density logs. The combination of these logs can help provide a comprehensive understanding of the structure and behavior of supercritical carbon dioxide. And knowing the physical properties of the CO₂ at different combinations of P and T is mandatory for a comprehensive Formation Evaluation

Figure 3. Phase diagram of CO₂

and to identify the proper parameters to feed the equation used in the process. For this reason in the next chapter, we will analyze and discuss the most important physical properties that can affect logging measurements and relative interpretation.

5.1 Density

Batzle and Wang (1992) developed a technique to compute the density and bulk modulus during the research of pore fluid seismic characteristics. Fig. 4 shows the relation between the density of carbon dioxide and pressure, the diagram which will be used as a reference was produced by using Xu's formula: (Batzle and Wang 1992, Xu 2006)

Figure 4. Reference CO₂ density values at various pressure and temperature. (Batzle and Wang 1992, Xu 2006)

$$\rho_{CO_2} = f_2(T, P) \quad (2)$$

Here ρ_{CO_2} is CO₂ density, f_2 is the specific factor, T is Temperature, °C, P is the pressure, MPa.

5.2 Hydrogen Index

A hydrogen index is calculated by dividing the number of hydrogen atoms per unit volume by the number of hydrogen atoms per unit volume of pure water at the surface. In other words, the hydrogen index (HI) tells us how dense hydrogen is in comparison to water. HI is determined as follows

$$HI = \frac{\text{Amount of hydrogen in sample}}{\text{Amount of hydrogen in pure water at STP}}$$

It is accepted that the hydrogen index of water is 1 at normal conditions, but it can be affected by factors such as temperature, salinity, and pressure. The hydrogen index is the property that affect Neutron porosity acquisition.

<i>HI (CH₄)</i>	<i>HI (CO₂)</i>	<i>HI (H₂O)</i>	<i>P (psi)</i>	<i>T °C</i>
0.41	0	0.97	5000	70
0.35	0	0.95	5000	110
0.31	0	0.92	5000	150
0.28	0	0.89	5000	200

Table 3. Hydrogen index for Carbon dioxide, methane and water

Hydrogen Index values are represented in Table.3 for a variety of fluids at fixed pressure but at different temperatures. The hydrogen index is a function of the quantity of hydrogen in the fluids, CO₂ has no hydrogen in the chemical formula so the real Hydrogen Index is zero, but the response on Neutron tools (with any type of source) are calibrated with rock of known composition and porosity, saturated with fresh water. So the real tool response in reservoir saturated with CO₂ will be an apparent neutron porosity affected by T and P of the system.

5.3 Acoustic velocity

The acoustic velocity of CO₂ was calculated using empirical measurement data. According to Han and others, the P-wave velocity of CO₂ varies with pressure and temperature as seen below:

$$v_p = f_1(T, P) \quad (3)$$

Figure 5. Reference CO₂ acoustic values at various pressure and temperature. (Han and Batzle 2010)

Where:

v_p – acoustic velocity, km/san

f_1 – specific function

T – Temperature, °C

P – Pressure, MPa

The acoustic velocity of CO₂ approaches that of a liquid phase under high-pressure condition and rise along with the increase of the pressure and falling temperature. Fig.5 illustrates how the acoustic velocity of supercritical CO₂ falls when temperature increases while the pressure remains stable, and the higher the pressure, the smaller the increase in amplitude.

Chapter 6. Well-logging

This chapter provides a comprehensive overview of the topic of log interpretation and explores the fundamental problems affecting a formation's prospective hydrocarbon output that well logs address. The borehole environment is defined in terms of how it affects electrical logging readings, and all qualitative concepts required for straightforward log interpretation are supplied. The main purpose of this section is assumed to be how to carry out downhole logging, obtain and examine gamma ray, neutron logging, density, and resistivity data for multiple liquid phases, and compare simulation results with real data from the well. Through well logging, we can measure physical properties of the rocks and determine their composition, variability and petrophysical characteristics close and around the borehole.

6.1 Natural Gamma Logging

The natural gamma log is the most straightforward radioactive approach used in geophysical well-logging. These logging devices keep track of the number of gamma-ray emissions from the rocks surrounding a borehole. The most basic of these technologies record merely the overall gamma-ray signal. Essentially, this signal is made up of gamma-ray emissions at various energies from the radioactive isotopes of the elements potassium (^{40}K), thorium (^{232}Th), and uranium (^{238}U) as well as their daughter products in the decay chain.

In addition to being greatly influenced by biological activity and subsurface processes, the distribution of K, Th, and U (and their daughter products) in the continental crust differs significantly. Because of this, recording the gamma-ray signal coming from the rocks around a borehole can reveal a lot of information about the geology and processes that have occurred. Shales and other clay-rich sediments have comparatively high natural gamma readings in sedimentary rock

sequences, whereas pure quartz sandstones and limestones have relatively low values. The higher readings found in clay-rich sediments are mostly caused by the clay minerals' affinity for potassium.

Density measurement is active nuclear logging because it is related with interaction of gamma rays emitted by a source with the atoms of the rock composition.

After being emitted in the formation by a source, gamma rays gradually lose energy as a result of collisions with other atoms in the rock (called Compton scattering). Gamma rays are scattered until their energy is low enough that the

Figure 6. a) Illustration of interpreted real gamma-ray log
 b) The comparison between simulated and acquired gamma ray logs

formation absorbs the ray completely. Because the gamma-ray photons lose their energy through scattering interactions with electrons, the distance that a gamma-ray photon can travel through rocks is significantly dependent on its electron density. In reality, gamma rays may penetrate as much as 1-2 meters through rocks, however, this is highly dependent on their beginning energy level and the density of the rock. Distances are higher in low-density rocks like extremely porous sediments and coals and considerably shorter in dense crystalline rocks. The total counts of the Gamma-ray recorded by two detectors are affected by electron density of the formation, which can be approximated to formation bulk density.

In order to properly interpret geological sections, gamma-ray data is typically combined with other well logs such as caliper and bit size. Fig.6a displays an interpreted gamma ray log with the caliper and bit sizes present. The interpretation has been verified by modifying the lithology for each layer of a small section of the same log as shown in fig.6b.

6.2 Neutron Porosity Logging

There are three main aspects to neutron logging: neutron emission, neutron scattering, and neutron absorption. Nuclear neutrons (4.5 MeV for AM-BE standard source) are emitted by the neutron tool through a radioactive source. Logging uses two different neutron sources: 1) alpha sources such as radium, plutonium, and americium, and 2) beryllium-9.

The neutrons entering the borehole wall from the tool are high in energy and have a strong penetrating power. Within the formation, fast neutrons interact with atom nuclei and neutron scattering occurs. Neutron scattering has 2 types: elastic and inelastic (Fig.7). Fast neutron collisions with heavy atomic nuclei can result in

inelastic scattering (Fig.7 b). The rebound nucleus may quickly lose its energy as gamma radiation or keep onto its excited metastable state for a while. Therefore, in inelastic scattering, there is no momentum conservation between the scattered neutron and the recoiling nucleus. Fast neutron collisions with large atomic number nuclei are the principal cause of inelastic scattering.

When a neutron collides with an atomic nucleus, it **scatters elastically**, like a

Figure 7. Elastic and inelastic neutron scattering

billiard ball hitting with another billiard ball (Fig.7 a). In elastic scattering some of the particle's kinetic energy is transferred to the other without kinetic energy being lost. The neutron loses some energy and slows down with every interaction (collision), whereas the atom's nucleus in the building material gets energy. These collisions happen with the nuclei of every element. Additionally, when the neutron and nucleus masses are equal, the process of energy transfer is most effective. When the formation material nuclei are more massive than the neutron, thus, the process of energy transfer is significantly less effective. The neutron weighs about the same as hydrogen atoms (the lightest element). As a result, interactions with hydrogen nuclei are the most efficient way for neutrons to lose energy by elastic scattering, while interactions with more heavy nuclei like

carbon or oxygen are far less effective. Fig. 8 illustrates how effectively different elements slow down fast neutrons.

In this circumstance, neutrons rapidly lose energy thanks to collisions with hydrogen nuclei and become "thermal neutrons." The thermal neutrons will eventually be captured by the nuclei of the atoms or absorbed by the formation's nucleus. The effectiveness of neutron absorption varies depending on the element. Only hydrogen and chlorine display considerable neutron absorption behavior and exist in considerable concentrations in rocks. The processes of neutron absorption by hydrogen and chlorine are described in detail.

Figure 8. For a clean sandstone $\phi = 0.15$, the hydrogen, silicon and oxygen fast neutron slowing efficiency is plotted as a function of neutron energy.

In many respects, these thermal neutrons act as diffusing gases and form a sphere around the source. Depending on the concentration of hydrogen around the probe, the radius of this sphere will vary. Neutrons are a generally excellent instrument for assessing "porosity," however it is important to keep in mind that measurements rely on the model used. More specifically:

- The pores are considered to be totally water-filled.
- The neutron tool only assesses the characteristics of the rocks that are extremely close to the borehole (i.e., there may be issues with drilling-induced changes)
- The neutron log data are affected by changes in borehole diameter.

For these reasons, neutron tool should be calibrated in order to get a more accurate response. A neutron porosity measurement can be significantly impacted by three formation properties: the rock fabric's lithology, shale mineral content, and gas or low-density hydrocarbons in the pores.

Lithology-effect

The so-called "lithology effect" describes the phenomenon that, for only limestone, when the neutron tool is calibrated in a water-filled limestone formation, the output in limestone units is numerically equivalent to the water-filled porosity. The neutron tool would read a little bit lower than the actual porosity in a sandstone formation with the same water-filled porosity when applying this calibration. The tool calibrated for limestone would display a rather higher porosity in the case of a dolomitic deposit. The neutron log, which is generally labeled in "limestone" units, will thus typically only read correctly in limestone that has been filled with fresh water. If labeled in "sandstone" units, it will only read correctly in formations made of sandstone. The impact of applying improper lithology transform is indicated in fig.9. The density and neutron logs are both displayed in units of limestone porosity.

Because the dolomite grain density is higher than that of limestone in zone 4, water-filled dolomite, the density reads as having a reduced apparent porosity, and the curve shifts to the right as a result. However, the neutron porosity in zone 4 overestimates the porosity by around 2.3 porosity unit (p.u). Because the grain density of sandstone is lower than that of limestone, the density in zone 3 reads

somewhat greater apparent porosity. When the limestone transform is applied, the neutron porosity underestimates the real porosity by roughly 4.5 p.u.

Shale-effect

One of the features of neutron porosity logs is that they show comparatively high readings of actual porosity in shale zones. It's frequently believed that associated trace elements with high thermal capture cross sections are the source of the inaccuracy in thermal porosity readings in shales. In spite of the inclusion of

Figure 9. The response of neutron and density logs to various lithologies, fluid contents, and borehole condition

thermal absorbers, clays and shales provide a challenge for any neutron porosity

interpretation due to the hydroxyls linked with the clay mineral structure. The high hydrogen content present in the shale matrix is the main cause of the high apparent porosity values. Zone 9 of Fig. 9 depicts an example of the shale impact. The apparent neutron porosity on a "sandstone" matrix in this example surpasses the density porosity in the two zones where the high gamma ray reading would typically indicate the presence of shale.

Gas effect

Neutron porosity tools are calibrated in rocks with liquid-filled porosity. This is due to the fact that the gas filling the pores has a significant influence on the formation's slowing down length and, consequently, on the apparent porosity. The neutron slowing-down length rises when the water component of the formation is partially replaced by a considerably less dense gas, which causes the apparent porosity to diminish. The actual porosity, the water saturation, the gas density, as well as the lithology all have a role in how porosity decreases. The bulk density of the formation is similarly reduced when the fluid in the pores is substituted with less dense gas. Well, logging exploits these two effects by measuring porosity and density simultaneously, as described in figure 9.

The gas impact is visible in zone 7 of Fig.9, which is marked "hydrocarbon effects."

6.3 Resistivity Logging

Resistivity logging is a measurement of a formation's resistivity or resistance to the passage of an electric current. It's measured by resistivity tools. The majority of rock materials are fundamentally insulators, whereas their enclosing fluids are conductors. Resistivity logs are critical data in formation evaluation since they are used to calculate water saturation, an input parameter for assessing hydrocarbon resources. Logging devices often convey resistivity logs using electric wireline or Logging While Drilling LWD equipment. There are two

modern types of resistivity recording techniques available today: On the left historical Dual Laterolog with an electrical focusing system while on the right basic dual coil system (induction tool) (fig 10). The Laterolog was designed to provide reliable formation resistivity data in wells drilled with salt water muds. The Dual Laterolog presents two resistivity readings at various depths into the formation: deep and shallow. Here, focusing currents drive the current beam horizontally into the formation. Both the measurements and the focusing currents come back to a distant electrode on the surface across a considerable distance for the deep survey. As a result, the investigation's depth is substantially increased, and the influence of nearby formations and borehole conductivity is minimized. The induction device was designed to measure conductivities deeply embedded

Figure. 10 Basic configuration for Laterolog and Induction equipment:

in the formation with the minimal possibility of invasion zone disruption. The device has transmitter coils that emit a high-frequency AC current, causing eddy

currents to form in the nearby area. Most of these eddy currents are concentrated beyond the normal flushed zone's diameter, and their size roughly corresponds to the virgin formation's conductivity. Because the induction instrument directly measures conductivity rather than resistivity, more accurate results are typically obtained in lower resistivity sections.

Wireline-based resistivity devices are often used in static wells, when the invasion of mud filtrate has practically finished because of the formation of mud cake on the borehole wall, hence reducing the influence of dynamic invasion. The LWD tools, in contrast, are used while the well is being drilled and are thus exposed to the dynamic environments of the drilling process.

Chapter 7. Analysis of the pure fluid response of CO₂ for density, neutron, and sigma

7.1 Validation of UtapWels response against benchmark situation

As a preliminary measure before proceeding with the building of synthetic well-logs, and the simulations, we evaluated the performance of the simulator in order to minimize the possibility of serious errors occurring. The first validation comes from the comparison of Porosity Effects on photoelectric factors between UtapWels, and the reference values from Log Interpretation Chart (Schlumberger), using the same lithology composition, fluids, and petrophysical properties. Since PEF measurement is sensitive to elements with a high atomic number, it is a useful technique for detecting different types of reservoir rocks. The values for pure liquids are almost identical in table 4 and table 5, as shown.

Reference values of PEF			
Matrix	Porosity	100% H ₂ O	100% CH ₄
Quartz	0	1.81	1.81
	0.35	1.54	1.76
Calcite	0	5.08	5.08
	0.35	4.23	4.96
Dolomite	0	3.14	3.14
	0.35	2.66	3.07

Table 4. Reference photoelectric factor values for pure water and methane

Porosity Effect on Photoelectric factor by UtapWels				
Matrix	Porosity	100% H ₂ O	100% CH ₄	100% CO ₂
Quartz	0	1.805	1.805	1.8
	0.35	1.539	1.752	1.69
Calcite	0	5.08	5.08	5.08
	0.35	4.23	4.96	4.71
Dolomite	0	3.14	3.14	3.14
	0.35	2.66	3.05	2.93

Table 5. Simulated photoelectric factor values for pure water, methane and carbon dioxide

The simulated result was enhanced by adding a column to calculate the photoelectric factor for CO₂. Based on this comparison, we are able to confirm the reliability of the simulator's performance. The density of CO₂ will also be a crucial consideration for validating UtapWels results. The second step of validation was performed on the density of CO₂ on P-T sensitivity.

We compared the results of the calculations of CO₂ bulk density at different temperatures and different pressures with a data set sorted out by NIST and used as a benchmark. NIST is a National Institute of Standard and Technology by the US Department of Commerce, and in the web site the NIST chemistry Handbook delivers accurate thermophysical properties for several fluids to be used as reference properties. These data include also the Density and velocity of fluids.

The comparison of variation of pure CO₂ between curves generated from the NIST chemistry handbook with those from UTNuPro measurement reference provided by UtapWels show similar values and similar trends and the variation in absolute values is within acceptable tolerance as indicated in fig.11. This test indicates that also for density of pure fluid the simulated values generated using UtapWels are in line with benchmark expectations.

We perform the same test also for pure CO₂ neutron porosity and sigma, using as a benchmark some unpublished and reserved data delivered by a service company within a collaboration with ENI. We cannot provide results of this test given a non-disclosure agreement between ENI and the service company, but we observed some important differences between the two data sets for Neutron Porosity (Hydrogen Index), while Sigma was in line with the benchmark values. We believe that the simulation sort out by UtapWels is in line with technical expectations and ENI will reserve the opportunity to further discuss with the service company the discrepancy observed.

After having performed this step of verification and assessing the reliability of the UtapWels response as described above, we moved in generating charts of physical properties of pure CO₂ at Pressure and Temperature variation. These charts will be very useful in defining physical properties to be used as input parameters for

Fig 11. The diagram represents the relationship between bulk densities of carbon dioxide produced from two different sources at various pressure and temperature.

further formation evaluation with reservoir involving CO₂ as fluid in combination with other fluids.

7.2 Density simulation

The density of supercritical fluid varies with pressure and temperature. CO₂ density increases with pressure and decreases with temperature.

Fig 12. The graph depicts the calculated CO₂ density values vs pressure

Fig.12 shows that the density of CO₂ is approximately 1 g/cm³ at 70°C, but at 170°C at 10000 psi pressure, it is only 0.69 g/cm³ so this result agrees with that of the reference diagram shown in figure 3. In addition to rising density caused by rising pressure, this also means that as the depth of the supercritical CO₂ increases, so does its density as well. A diagram showing the bulk density of CO₂ at different temperatures is shown in the Fig.12; these endpoints will be taken into account in the interpretation of the logs later on.

7.3 Neutron simulation

Measuring reservoir porosity through hydrogen index and monitoring the movement of injected CO₂ in the subsurface through Sigma, is critical both for optimal open hole formation evaluation and CO₂ storage operation management and meeting regulatory standards.

Neutron tools are the technology that supervised both these needs. As we have already discussed in chapter 6 borehole neutron tools can measure porosity or sigma based on a different mode of acquisition to investigate different products of interactions between neutrons emitted by a source and formation nuclei.

In neutron porosity mode, the ratio between the count rate ratio of the long-space detector and the short-space detector is converted in neutron porosity through conversion functions generated by primary tool calibrations. Open hole Neutron porosity is used in combination with density for porosity evaluation and fluid

Fig 13. Simulated neutron values of CO₂ at various pressure and temperature

identification with particular added values in gas identification. In this research, the neutron characteristics of CO₂ have been obtained by building a synthetic rock model where total porosity is 100% (0% matrix) filled with pure CO₂ at a certain temperature and pressure. A simulation for the limestone neutron porosity was performed using the UT-longhorn-WL simulation tool.

The results of simulations are graphically expressed in the chart of Figure 13 where it is apparent that CO₂ neutron values are increasing as pressure increases and decreasing as temperature increases. Fig. 13 illustrates the neutron porosity values of CO₂ within the range of -0.12 to -0.15. The magnitude of these values

is huge and should be non-neglected when using neutron data in a CO₂ environment. When comparing the neutron porosity values of CO₂ and CH₄, we found that the values of these properties differed by a significant amount in terms of the limestone neutron porosity. Simulation results depend on several factors, including the simulation tool used, and calibration. Since CO₂ has essentially negligible slowing down power as a result of its zero hydrogen index and its low density. Furthermore, the neutron tool response is characterized through calibration using a block of rock of known matrix (Limestone as ENI standard) and porosity saturated with fresh water, it is clear that simulated pure neutron values of CO₂ represent apparent hydrogen index values that should be taken into account during parametrization of equation utilized for formation valuation in reservoir saturated with CO₂. From a theoretical perspective, the simulation results seem to be robust and usable.

7.4 Sigma simulation

Pulsed Neutron Logs (PNL) are by far the most often used method for measuring a characteristic capture cross section known as “Sigma”. As a result of PNL

Fig 14. Simulated sigma values of CO₂ at various pressure and temperature

logging, it is possible to identify the reservoir fluids nearby the wells. It is a technology used mainly in cased hole applications for monitoring and time lapse purpose, and it can also help monitor the migration of injected CO₂ from one well to another during injection phase.

A typical pulsed neutron logging instrument consists of a neutron source and two gamma-ray detectors about 1m away and 15cm apart. These, together with the power supply and down-hole instruments, are placed in a thin enclosure with an exterior diameter of around 50 mm. The neutron source produces dense bursts of fast neutrons by fusing deuterium and tritium nuclei. The bursts last around 0.1 milliseconds and produce 50,000 to 100,000 fast neutrons. Because of collision with nuclei in the borehole fluid, fast neutrons are slowed to thermal velocities. Once the neutrons have slowed to thermal energies, they can be caught by particular nuclei, producing a secondary gamma-ray with a particular energy. Measuring the total amount of Gamma rays emitted by capture reactions is the way to derive Sigma that which is a measurement related to formation capture capability. The Capture capability is related to the presence of specific elements and Chlorine is the most common element in nature with higher capture capability, followed by Hydrogen.

Neutron values for CO₂ have a low sigma value, which explains the low density and the poor thermal neutron capture ability of carbon and oxygen.

Fig.14 shows that the sigma values for carbon dioxide increase with increasing Pressure (at the same Temperature), and decrease with increasing Temperature (at the same pressure). But must be noted how the range of sigma is very low and narrow. The range, for the adopted P/T, is between 0.02 c.u. and 0.06 c.u. This chart and the related values must be carefully taken into account when interpreting Sigma for monitoring purpose.

7.5 Acoustic velocity

For acoustic velocity of pure CO₂, we have used the reference from National Institute of Standards and Technology website. The response from the UtapWels

simulation appears not realistic. Eni will further discuss with Austin University the issues encountered in simulating acoustic velocity for pure fluid CO₂ at different pressure and Temperature.

In Fig.15 results and chart have been reported and we can easily detect phase transition at low temperature and pressure conditions. CO₂ behaves very differently in liquid and supercritical states, depending on whether it is in a liquid or supercritical state. Also, this chart would be used for parametrization processes in further Formation evaluation workflow.

Fig 15. Relationship between CO₂ acoustic velocity and pressure, derived from the website of National Institute of Standards and Technology

Chapter 8. Building synthetic well-logs for several scenarios in CO₂ Injection and storage project

The growing interest in carbon capture and storage (CCS) projects drives in-depth research across several disciplines. The phase for monitoring at the so-called spy wells, in particular, is crucial for a good understanding of carbon dioxide (CO₂) plume growth distant from the injectors. In this regard, time-lapse pulsed neutron logging (PNL) is a cornerstone for quantitatively assessing fluid saturation changes behind casing. But, if CO₂ injection is conducted into depleted gas stores, the latter operation may become challenging.

This chapter deals with a deep study of various PNL measurements for fluid identification and saturation monitoring purposes in CCS projects. The basic physics behind the measurement includes the generation of high-energy neutrons (about 14 MeV), their interactions (inelastic, elastic and capture) with borehole and formation elements, and the time and energy based analysis of the induced gamma rays. Monte Carlo N-Particle nuclear modeling represents a rigorous way to interpret PNL measurements in a given completion, borehole fluid, cement placement quality and rock/formation fluid scenario. However, UtapWels includes the log response modeling of interest for our aim: in fact, the PNL curves considered in this paper are the neutron capture cross-section and neutron porosity.

In order to generate such theoretical pulsed neutron tool responses for given logging conditions, we have modeled certain scenarios based on certain assumptions. There are several inputs that are used in the modeling process, including the formation lithology, the formation fluid composition, the temperature and pressure in the reservoir, the water saturation, and the concentration of CO₂ that has been injected into it. As a result, each of these factors is taken into account when developing an effective saturation estimation in the PNL log data analysis. As part of the PNL modeling process, it is important

to consider the possibility that there are a number of factors that can have an impact on the results of the model, including:

- Due to variations in formation lithology, fluid saturations can be underestimated or overestimated due to slight changes in formation lithology.
- The presence of borehole fluid. (There is the possibility that some of the injected carbon dioxide could be dissolved in the fluid. Even if this would not have a significant effect on log response, it would be better to consider)

The methodology is presented and discussed through a case study application performed on a spy well drilled into a depleted gas-bearing reservoir. This consists of more than three thousand meters of shaly-sand sequences characterized by medium-to-high porosity values and the formation water salinity is about 35 ppk. In order to evaluate CO₂ plume migration in the reservoir, first of all, we tried to create a base model (using 3D UtapWels) that would reflect the geological environment existed before injection was introduced into the system. The structure of our model is based on the assumption that there are six geological layers, which alternate with layers of sandstone and shale. Quartz, Muscovite, and Orthoclase are assumed to make up the matrix composition, and it's accepted that reservoirs have a porosity of 0.21, while the shale layer has a porosity of 0.15. Basically, the model has two wells - one is for the monitoring of CO₂ arrival and the other is for the injection. The first is the spy-well, focus of this work. Due to the fact that the layers are not very thick, the temperature is assumed to be 55°C at each interval. There are three layers that are regarded as reservoirs - layer two, layer four, and layer six - that have a pressure of 75, 52, and 93 bars respectively, and a water saturation rate of 74% in those layers. Now, we have three possible scenarios, those are to build synthetic well-logs on the basis of the baseline model, after a year after injection, and after two years after the second injection. The CO₂ migration, CO₂-CH₄ mixing and saturation changes come from the outcomes of

the available 3D dynamic reservoir model. In the following chapter, we will be discussing this topic in more detail.

8.1 Case N.1 Pre-injection period and the base model

It was at first necessary to create the synthetic log for all geological layers of the pre-injection period before the injection. Fig.16 represents the pre-injection period base model and stratigraphy starting from shale lithological point of view.

Layers N ^o	Temperature	Pressure	S _w
1	55°C	330 bar	100 %
2	55°C	72 bar	74 %
3	55°C	330 bar	100 %
4	55°C	52 bar	74 %
5	55°C	330 bar	100 %
6	55°C	93 bar	74 %

Table 6. Characteristics of base model layers

Here 1st, 3rd, and 5th layers are shale while the 2nd, 4th and 6th layers are sandstone mainly made up of quartz, muscovite, and orthoclase minerals. As shown in fig.17, we have obtained the gamma-ray, neutron 14Mev, neutron Am/Be, resistivity, and sigma responses based on a simulation of a realistic scenario. Characteristics of the layers have been shown in table 6 for base model.

Log responses (as shown in fig.17) indicate that Gamma-ray value for shale layers is around 170 API while for sandstone layers it is about 107 API. Because sandstone contains silicates, it has a higher gamma ray value. A 100% water liquid composition is assumed for the shale layers in the current model, while a 26% methane gas composition is considered for the reservoirs. This means that

while the 1st, 3rd, and 5th layers appear to have lower resistivity but higher sigma values, however, reservoirs

Figure 16. The base model

show a high resistivity and low sigma. As a matter of fact, sigma of water is higher of sigma of CH₄ due to the presence of salt in it. In the end, after the

Figure 17. Well logs for the base model

injection of CO₂, the 3D dynamic reservoir model predicts that only in the 4th some saturation changes occurred. We'll discuss it in following case.

8.2 Case N.2. CO₂ injection (1 year) and tool response.

This period refers to the time one year after the CO₂ injection. The arrival of the CO₂ plume could be monitored by checking variations from log response. In our

Layers N°	Temperature	Pressure	S _w
1	55°C	330 bar	100 %
2	55°C	77 bar	74 %
3	55°C	330 bar	100 %
4	55°C	61 bar	58 %
5	55°C	330 bar	100 %
6	55°C	95 bar	74 %

Table 7. CO₂ Injected model characteristics

analysis, we assumed that as the pressure in the reservoir increased as a result of the injection of CO₂ (as indicated in fig.18), water saturation would decrease in the second reservoir while the parameters for the shale layers would still remain unchanged, stated in table 7.

Figure 18. Model depicting after injection period

As predicted injected CO₂ will mix with CH₄ at the beginning of the process. In this case the ratio between methane and carbon dioxide is as follows CH₄:CO₂=0.26:0.74

It can be seen from well-log data (Fig.19) that after injection there is a decrease in neutron and density values due to CO₂ having lower neutron and sigma values compared to CH₄, so the expansion between two tracks is called as "gas effect".

Figure 19. Well logs after injection

Density is here simulated only for reference. The actual monitoring PNL measurements are neutron and sigma. Although the arrival of carbon dioxide at the spy well can be defined, determining its concentration from PNL is difficult. In fact, CH₄ and CO₂ at this pressure and temperature regimes are very similar for the PNL standpoint. Although the arrival of carbon dioxide at the spy well can be defined, determining its concentration is difficult.

Case N.3. CO₂ injection (2 years) and tool response.

After two years, due to the increase in CO₂ amount, pressure in the reservoir increased. Upon 2 years of injection, it takes into account the arrival of a significant concentration of carbon dioxide plume. In this case, Carbon dioxide and methane have a volume ratio of 0.87: 0.13 and characteristics have been indicated in table 8.

CO₂ plumes have already reached the spy well with greater concentration than in the previous year, as shown in fig.20. A larger expansion between density logs (still for reference) and neutron logs is also evident in tool response. Sigma values,

Layers N°	Temperature	Pressure	S _w
1	55°C	330 bar	100 %
2	55°C	79 bar	74 %
3	55°C	330 bar	100 %
4	55°C	63 bar	58 %
5	55°C	330 bar	100 %
6	55°C	96 bar	74 %

Table 8. CO₂ Injected model characteristics

Figure 20. Model showing the period after 2 years of injection

however, did not change significantly. As lithology and salinity did not change during the 3 phases, resistivity and gamma-ray logs have not changed, since resistivity depends on electrically conductive water, and gamma-ray reflects lithology.

Figure 21. Tool repose after 2 years of injection

The outcome of the last scenario is shown in Figure 21, then we combined the capture cross section readings for all scenarios. The first case is where the reservoir layer contains pure CH₄, giving a capture unit of 14.7, while in the second case sigma value declined to 13.29 capture unit then to 13.2 in the last model. We can see that the difference between the sigma values is solely due to the CO₂ injection, which means that when methane is replaced by carbon dioxide, the mixed fluid's ability to capture neutrons is reduced.

Based on the tool response of the base model compared to the post-injection model, the difference is almost 1.5 cu, which is close to the accepted minimum uncertainty value (fig.22).

The Pressure for the first well log is assumed to be 754 psi and the fluid

Figure 22. Capture cross section (Sigma) responses for 3 cases

composition is 100% CH₄, and the second log response pressure is 884 psi and

Figure 23. Sigma values for CH₄ and its mixture with CO₂ in pre-injection and post-injection period

the fluid composition is 74% CO₂, 26% CH₄. In the 3rd case, pressure has increased to 913.7 psi, and accordingly, the composition ratio between the two phases is so: 87% CO₂, 13% CH₄. This result is not confident enough to determine the arrival and movement of CO₂ plumes in the reservoir. Even with increased

Figure 24. Neutron limestone porosity values for CH₄ and its mixture with CO₂

CO₂ injections, there is no difference in response between the second and third cases. More accurately, variation in sigma values of the gases has been shown in Figure 23. The simulation result illustrates that for this case study sigma is not a suitable method to discriminate CO₂ and CH₄. On the other hand, neutron porosity for methane and carbon dioxide differs, as illustrated in figure 24, so representing a better monitoring strategy.

As the pressure increases, the change in the neutron value of the single CO₂ phase and the methane & carbon dioxide mixture increases.

It is worth mentioning that these outcomes only hold for the case study just discussed. Different values of water salinity, pressure, temperature, initial water saturation, and time-lapse mixtures of CH₄ and CO₂ will change sigma and neutron accordingly, possibly providing better diagnostic capabilities of PNL measurements.

Chapter 9. Validating formation evaluation of a reservoir containing CO₂

Validating formation evaluation involves real logging data acquired from a well, interpretation by a geophysicist, and simulation of interpreted logs. Borehole logging of a reservoir containing CO₂ was performed in the aspect of gamma ray, neutron, density, and resistivity.

Figure 25. Interpreted real well-logs

At the first stage of this study, the obtained well-log data was interpreted by a geophysicist as described in (fig.25). The interpretation shows the lithology is mainly made up of dolomite and limestone sequences, and contains CH₄ and CO₂. Geophysicist's interpretation was based on a probabilistic approach that uses the simulated pure neutron and density response of CO₂ (see Chapter 7). Then, interpreted a small interval (70ft) was taken and simulated (fig.26). The

Figure 26. The figure represents real and simulated well-logs comparison

simulation process has been fulfilled and synthetic well logs are generated by modifying each petrophysical layer, meaning lithology, matrix composition, saturated water content, and present liquid content according to the result presented by the interpretation.

The goal was to determine whether an interpretation from the geophysicist was adequate and match the real log data. As can be seen from Fig.26, there is a good match between almost all simulated tracks and real acquired data (Gamma ray, Density, Neutron, and Resistivity), but there are still some small variations in neutron response in the range of 12560 m and 12570 m depth. However, minor variations are negligible and the simulation results confirm the validity of the interpretation based also on some end-points delivered by our simulations on pure CO₂ fluid response.

Conclusion

The purpose of this study was to determine the effect of CO₂ on log response and how it might be dealt with for sound evaluation. The Experimental part of the study was generated using an advanced log simulator developed by the University of Austin. Main results:

- ✓ Possible migration pathways of CO₂ has been discussed, faults and lack of sealing ability of caprock are the most responsible for carbon dioxide leakage has been indicated.
- ✓ Endpoints for pure CO₂ were generated for density, sigma, and neutron and acoustic velocity.
- ✓ Based on quantitative analysis and validated simulations of single-phase and multi-phase CO₂ characteristics, it is observed that naturally occurring or injected CO₂ can increase the fluid density while decreasing the ability of the fluid to catch neutrons.
- ✓ Neutron has been selected as a suitable way to monitor CO₂ movement in the reservoir, while the sigma method was incapable of detecting CO₂ in the specific environment analysed for this study.
- ✓ Validation of a real Formation Evaluation on a carbonate reservoir containing CO₂, performed using as an input end-point derived from pure CO₂ fluid simulation, confirms the reliability of the charts generated for supporting Log interpretation.

Reference

- [1] HOLLOWAY, S., PEARCE, J.M., OHSUMI, T. AND HARDS, V.L.2005. A Review of Natural CO₂ Occurrences and their Relevance to CO₂ Storage. British Geological Survey External Report, CR/05/104, 117pp
- [2] Zhaowen Li, Mingzhe Dong, Shuliang Li, Sam Huang CO₂ sequestration in depleted oil and gas reservoirs caprock characterization and storage capacity 25 August 2005
- [3] S. A. Hertel, B. C. Anger, K. Smith, M. Appel 21-26 August 2016
- [4] Yitian Xiao, Gordon Macleod, David M. Advocate, Chris Reaves, Robert J. Pottorf: Natural CO₂ occurrence in geological formations and the implications on CO₂ storage capacity and site selection 2011
- [5] B.A.Copper, M.J.Raven, L.Samuel, Hardjono, W.Satoto Origin and Geological controls on subsurface CO₂ distribution with examples from western Indonesia May, 1997
- [6] Helen Wycherley, Andrew Fleet, Harry Shaw Some observations on the origins of large volumes of carbon dioxide accumulations in sedimentary basins 9 August 1999
- [7] Baozhi Pan, Jian Lei, Lihua Zhang¹ and Yuhang Guo: Research on the physical properties of supercritical CO₂ and the log evaluation of CO₂-bearing volcanic reservoirs 3 July 2017
- [8] Tongwei Zhang, Mingjie Zhang, Baojun Bai, Xianbin Wang, and Liwu Li: Origin and accumulation of carbon dioxide in the Huanghua depression, Bohai Bay Basin, China
- [9] Well logging for earth scientists second edition Darwin V. Ellis, Julian M. Singer ISBN 978-1-4020-3738-2 (HB)
- [10] The Geological Interpretation of Well Logs Second edition, Malcolm Rider, Rider-French Consulting Ltd
- [11] Jason Braunberger, John Hamlinga, Charles Goreckia, Howard Millerb, Jim Rawsonb, Fred Walshb, Eric Pasternackb, Wayne Rowec, Robert Butschc, Edward Steadmana, John Harju: Characterization and time-lapse monitoring utilizing pulsed-neutron well logging: associated CO₂ storage at a commercial CO₂ EOR project, 2014.
- [12] ALLARD, P., DAJLEVIC, D. and DELARUE, C. 1989. Origin of carbon dioxide emanation from the 1979 Dieng eruption, Indonesia: Implications for the origin of the 1986 Nyos catastrophe. Journal of Volcanology and Geothermal Research, Vol. 39, 195-206.
- [13] BAKLID A, KORBUL R and OWREN G. 1996. Sleipner Vest CO₂ disposal, CO₂ injection into a shallow underground aquifer. SPE paper 36600, presented at

- 1996 SPE Annual Technical Conference and Exhibition, Denver Colorado, USA. 6-9 October 1996.
- [14] Jize Piao,1 Weon Shik Han, Sungwook Choung, and Kue-Young Kim, Dynamic Behavior of CO₂ in a Wellbore and Storage Formation: Wellbore-Coupled and Salt-Precipitation Processes during Geologic CO₂ Sequestration
- [15] Voormeij DA, Simandl GJ. Geological, ocean and mineral CO₂ sequestration options: A technical review. *Geosci Can* 2004;31:11–22.
- [16] Herzog H, Eliasson B, Kaarstad O. Capturing greenhouse gases. *Sci Am* 2000(Feb):72–9.
- [17] Wilson M, Monea M. IEA GHG Weyburn CO₂ Monitoring and Storage Project, Summary report 2000–2004. From the proceedings of seventh international conference on greenhouse gas control technologies, September, 2004;Vancouver, Canada.
- [18] Li S, Dong M, Li Z, Huang S, Qing H, Nickel E. Gas breakthrough pressure for hydrocarbon reservoir seal rocks: implications of the security of long-term CO₂ storage in the Weyburn field. *Geofluids* 2005;5 (4), in press.
- [19] Ren QY, Chen GJ, Yan W, Guo TM. Interfacial tension of (CO₂ + CH₄) + water from 298 K to 373 K and pressures up to 30 MPa. *J Chem Eng Data* 2000;45:610–2.
- [20] Yan W, Zhao GY, Chen GJ, Guo TM. Interfacial tension of (methane + nitrogen) + water and (carbon dioxide + nitrogen) + water. *J Chem Eng Data* 2001;46:1544–8.
- [21] Li Z, Dong M, Li S, Dai L. Densities and solubilities for binary systems of carbon dioxide + water and carbon dioxide + brine at 59 C and pressures to 29 MPa. *J Chem Eng Data* 2004;49:1026–31.
- [22] Li Z, Dong M, Li S, Dai L. A new method for gas effective diffusion coefficient measurement in brine-saturated porous rocks under high pressures. *J Porous Media*, in press.
- [23] Srivastava RK, Huang SS, Dong M. Laboratory investigation of Weyburn CO₂ miscible flooding. *J Can Pet Technol* 2000;39(2): 41–51
- [24] Myers, G., Nuclear Logging, Chapter 3D, Reservoir Engineering and Petrophysics Volume V(A), Petroleum Engineering Handbook, Edward Holstein, Editor, 2007. (Pages V-267 to V-287 for neutron logs).
- [25] Bassiouni, Z., Theory, Measurement and Interpretation of Well Logs, SPE Textbook Volume 4, 1994.
- [26] M.N. Anwara, A. Fayyaza, N.F. Sohaila, M.F. Khokharb, M. Baqara, W.D. Khana, K. Rasoolc, M. Rehand, A.S. Nizami: CO₂ capture and storage: A way forward for sustainable environment 14 August 2018
- [27] Amber Conner, David Chaceb, Jehad Abou-Saleh, Yonghwee Kimb, Caitlin McNeil, Jacqueline Gerst, Mark Kelleya, Matt Place, Rick Pardinic, and Neeraj Gupta Developing best practices for evaluating fluid saturations with pulsed neutron capture logging across multiple active CO₂-EOR fields, 2017

